

SIMPLIFICATION COMPOUND WORDS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The article describes the simplification of compound words. Examples of the fact that simplification also took place in the structure of the compound words widely used in the current Uzbek language are covered. Changes in the composition of words, mainly such as Sound Exchange, displacement in sounds, sound fall, were the reasons for the absorption of morphemes in the composition of words with each other. It has been shown that other changes, such as the phenomenon of redivision in the composition of a word, also occur as a result of the recorded sound changes.*

Keywords: *portable meaning, wordshakl, phenomenon of specialization, simplification, identity ratio, verb, core-base, incremental ratio, etymology, sound, place-sharing, homonymic, morpheme composition, form-forming addition, Sound Exchange, absorption, sound fall, comparison, word tar.*

The word forms of “bur and bura” (screw and twist) in the modern Uzbek language require a separate explanation. The verb “burmoq” (twist) is defined as a six-meaning word in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", and its first and second meanings are "to change the direction of movement, to flex to a side; to turn to a certain direction, to rotate ". The third meaning is recorded as a metaphorical meaning and is recorded in the form of diverting, predisposing. The fourth meaning is “to collect” actually given as a mistake. In this place, it is used in the sense of sewing. Let's pay attention to an example: Ziyodakhan ... twisted the mouth bag again (A. Qahhor) in the sentence it is said about, "to sew the mouth of the bag with an awl in a pell-mell method or a large seam".

The fifth meaning is given as to turn, to control. The sixth meaning is defined as squeezing, pinching, and examples “ He twisted his hand. The golden ring screwed my finger...are given [Volume 1, 380] inappropriately. Because in these sentences, it is observed that the verb “buramoq” (revolve) is used not the verb “bur”(twist). However, the verbs to twist and revolve are given in the dictionary as separate units.

It seems that in Uzbek, the verb “burmoq” means to turn something in a certain direction, to turn it in one direction without continuation, at the level of one attempt: as in he turned the car, he turned his head. In this case, it is not possible to use the car or head with the verb twist.

On page 375 of this dictionary, the verb to twist is recorded as a word with four meanings as the followings: a) "to rotate, to turn": b) "to wrap, twist and turn into spiral shape"; v) "to twirl and fix"; g) "to actuate spring mechanisms".

It is said that the origin of this word form is formed from the verb “bur” which means "rotate many times in a circle" in "EDUL" with the suffix -a with the meaning "repetition" [EDTL, 11,265] ; In Uzbek, the vowel “a” has changed to the vowel “ä”: marked as bur-+a=bura→burä [page 68].

It seems that the words *bur* and *bura* in Uzbek: a) definitely related to each other according to their origin b) the original meaning of both words is related. That is, to direct something in one direction. However, in the word *bura*, the action of orientation is performed continuously. This indicates a change in movement. So, *bur* represents a one-time action, discontinuous action, while *bura* represents a continuous action.

With the passage of time, the meaning of the verb *bura* "to direct in one direction continuously" has moved away from the meaning of "to direct once" expressed by the verb *bur*, a process of specialization in meaning has occurred. In the present case, for example, it cannot be used in the way "turned the nut", nor can it be used in the way "twisted the car". Both verbs have become a unit that expresses a separate action. The affix -a in the verb *bura* was assimilated with the core, and happened a process of simplification. Such a situation is observed in these pairs: qo'zi-qo'zg'a, qo'zg'at; alji-aljira, jim-jimi.

We can see that the process of simplification has occurred in the modern Uzbek words og'ana (ag'ana), ag'dar, og'dir. These words contain in the composition the root ag' (og'moq). In fact, the word og'ir (heavy) is related to this root. The first word in the line has the composition og'+in+a, where -in is an indicator of active voice, and -a is an intensifier of action. If the following word ag'dar is considered to consist of two parts, it can be seen that it contains the suffix -dar, an indicator of passive voice. The same condition with the last word. However, the word forms ag'dar and og'dir differed according to their meanings and their content was simplified, that is, the root part of these words has started to be useless. Its relation to the verb og'moq has started to disappear. This situation was the basis for simplification. The etymology of the Uzbek verbs og'moq, og'darmoq, ag'namoq, ag'anamoq is written in A. Mamatov's book "Etymological Observations" [T, 2010, page 74].

There has also been a simplification in the composition of the word forms o'rgan and o'rgat, which are widely used in the modern Uzbek language. It should be said that, first of all, in the composition of these word forms there is an exchange of sounds. That is, there is a change of g>r, and it has become o'gran→o'rgan. Because the root part of the word should be õg (mind, knowledge). If we remember, the stem of the verb o'qi is also related to this õg. In "Etymological Dictionary of Turkish Languages" (EDTL), the root of both verbs is considered to consist of the verb õ which means to know, understand, or the homonym form õg with meaning thought, mind, and many people agree with this idea. However, taking into account that the homonymic õg form is made from the verb õ through the element -ch, both verb stems can be considered as direct õ forms.

There are cases where the content of these words is interpreted in a different way. For example, in the "Short etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language" there is also an idea that the original morpheme composition of these verbs consists of ogur+a+n: o'gra+verb affix -a+-n is an indicator of active voice degree. (o'gran); o'gra+-a+-t (form of passive voice). In other sources, the separation of these verb forms into components is noted as well.

If we group the state of simplification in the above-mentioned words, we can note the following forms: 1) the preceding morpheme merges with the morpheme (stem morpheme) that follows it, and simplification occurs: da:ada→dada, ta+ og'a→tog'a; ach+yir→ayir (also ajrat) and so on:

2) simplification occurs when the next morpheme (word-forming or form-forming affix) is absorbed by the previous (usually root morpheme) morpheme, and this is often observed: turt, qurt, yirt, yiqit, tiril, tirik and others.

It is known that -t is an affix in constructions such as turt, yiqit, qurt, yrt (there are many words with this structure: qayt, ayt, yo'rt, surt, bo'rt, tort, yurt, o'rt, etc.), however, at present it is difficult to determine what morpheme it is; there is no doubt that the words "tiril" and "tirik" are derived from the same root. It is also known that the affixes -l and -k are used as derivatives in the composition: -l makes a verb, and it also means active voice: and -k makes an adjective, that is, both forms of words are made up of parts. However, the definition of the root part of these word forms is so noticeable that it requires a serious etymological analysis (it is not clear whether ti, tir or tiri is the root. Now it will not be possible to define such a meaningful part. Therefore, an oversimplification has occurred. Now both word forms are evaluated as root word forms, they cannot be divided into morphemes.

3) simplification occurs through the successive assimilation of the morphemes before and after the root with the root together: yutmoq, yilon, yiring, yuzum, yubor, etc.; the main root morpheme in the word yiring is in the form of -ir (-ar, er, -eri...), and the word-morpheme yi before it (in the meaning of accumulation) merges with the word-morpheme yir, and then the morpheme -ing was added to form a (mostly -n) noun, and finally these three morphemes merged with each other to form a simplification.

In the Uzbek language, the composition of the word forms ko'ndalang+iga, atrof+licha, o'g'rincha (-licha) often (-incha), qator+asiga, ko'tar+asiga, yolg'on+dakasiga, rosta+kamiga should be interpreted differently. To prove this situation, we will try to analyze the words yolg'ondakasiga or rostakamiga: if rost-stem morpheme (it is clear), what element will the part -aka or -akam be? The iga part is recorded as a separate affix [Grammar of the Uzbek language, T, Fan, 1975, 530]. If analyzed in this way, the rostakam part can also be evaluated as a compound word form. That is, the word form will have the structure rost+aka+-m+ iga. It can't be agree with that opinion. It seems that the elements known to us are rost, -m, -iga (-iga is an affix), but the part -aka remains unknown. If the rostakam part is clear and we take into account the fact that it is recorded in the dictionary [recorded in the large spelling dictionary, T, 1976, 355] and assuming that it is recorded in this way, if we consider the form -iga as a complex affix, the composition of the word will have the structure rost+akam+iga. It is also difficult to accept it: a) the individual use of the rostakam word form is very limited; b) Designation of part -iga as a complex affix is not yet sufficiently substantiated. Because it stands out -ga preposition of direction. Also, as long as the use of rostakam is recognized, the form of rostakami can also be recognized and recorded: rostakami is like this. So, dividing the word rostakami into morphemes remains problematic. It is better to evaluate it as a simplified word form. This is also confirmed by the word structure of the yolg'ondakasiga. That is, should this word form be separated in the form of yolg'on+-da+-ka+-siga or should it be separated in the style of yolg'on+-daka+-siga? The issue has not been resolved. Only yolg'on and -siga parts are recorded as separate units. It has become difficult to record the parts of -da, -qa (-daka, -daqqa) in the middle as units (it is impossible to consider them in the style of yolg'ondek+akasiga). In the Uzbek language, it is noted that this word also has a form of yolg'ondakamiga [that dictionary, 156]. Although the word form of yolg'ondakasiga is not recorded in the mentioned dictionary, in "Grammar of the Uzbek language" [1975, 530] this word

form is recorded as *yolg'ondakasiga*. The issue of giving this word form in the *yolg'ondaka* form (-daka) is also problematic.

Therefore, it is appropriate to include this word form in the simplified word form. Because the word forms of *yolg'onda* and *yolg'ondaka* are not observed separately

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